

IMPACT OF GLOBALISATION AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS ON SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA: SNAGS

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Abstract

This study examined the impact of globalisation and international relations on social development in Nigeria and its snags. The dependency theory was anchored in this study. This study employed a qualitative research methodology. The target population consisted of Nigerian academic scholars, researchers, and practitioners in Nigeria who have a background in mass communication and international relations. A purposive sampling technique was used to select participants with relevant expertise and experience in these domains. The sample size was determined to be 10 participants, which is deemed adequate for achieving qualitative data saturation while allowing for diverse viewpoints. Semi-structured interviews were used to collect data, and thematic analysis was employed to identify common themes, patterns, and insights across the responses. The findings revealed that globalisation significantly contributes to economic inequality and challenges social cohesion in Nigeria, as trade policy liberalisation tends to favour wealthy individuals and foreign corporations, thereby widening the income gap and fostering cultural dissonance among communities, particularly between the younger and older generations. The study concluded that while offering economic opportunities, globalisation has primarily deepened existing economic inequalities and strained social cohesion in Nigeria. The study recommended that the Nigerian government implement inclusive economic policies that prioritise the development of local industries and equitable wealth distribution to mitigate the adverse effects of globalisation on economic inequality and social cohesion.

Introduction

As a multifaceted process, globalisation entails the increasing interconnectedness and interdependence of countries through economic, political, cultural and social integration. International relations (IR) encompasses the strategic engagements between states and non-state actors in managing these interdependencies. Nigeria,

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with its significant demographic, economic, and political profile in Africa, has not been exempted from these processes. In fact, the forces of globalisation and international relations have played pivotal roles in shaping the trajectory of its social development. However, the Nigerian context reveals that these phenomena come with considerable challenges, or “snags,” that have impeded the optimal realisation of social development goals (Ihonvbere, 2017).

Social development broadly refers to the enhancement of societal well-being through improved living standards, equitable resource distribution, quality education, accessible healthcare, and stable social institutions. In Nigeria, the concept is closely related to poverty reduction, social cohesion, and human capital development. Understanding how globalisation and international relations affect these core elements of social development is crucial. According to Ake (2000), while globalisation promotes economic liberalisation and democracy, its impact on social development in Nigeria remains contested.

One of the critical variables influenced by globalisation is economic liberalisation. Policies encouraged by global financial institutions, such as the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the World Bank, including trade liberalisation and structural adjustment programmes, have aimed at integrating Nigeria into the global economy. However, these policies have contributed to increasing income disparities, with wealth concentrated among a few elites. Adedeji (2002) indicated that Nigeria’s openness to global trade and financial markets has led to growing inequality, which undermines social cohesion and broad-based social development.

The impact of globalisation on culture in Nigeria is another significant snag. The influx of foreign media and values has led to the gradual erosion of indigenous cultural norms and values. Suleiman (2018) argues that this cultural homogenisation threatens Nigeria’s social fabric, leading to identity crises among youths caught between traditional values and global cultural influences. This cultural disruption weakens the societal frameworks that are integral to promoting solidarity and cohesion within communities.

The political landscape of Nigeria and international relations are deeply intertwined, particularly in terms of governance. Global norms and diplomacy have partly driven Nigeria’s adoption of democratic principles. However, translating these principles into functional governance structures remains challenging. According to Falola (2020), international pressure on democratic reforms has often been met with resistance because of entrenched political corruption and ineffective institutions, which negatively impact efforts to foster social development.

Globalisation has brought both opportunities and challenges in the realm of health and social welfare. On the one hand, it has facilitated access to medical advancements and international aid in combating HIV/AIDS and malaria. The increasing privatisation of health care services due to global neoliberal policies has restricted access for the poor, worsening social inequality. In this regard, (2003) demonstrated that Nigeria’s international financial policies have led to reduced public funding for health services, thereby affecting social welfare systems.

Education is another critical variable affected by globalisation. Although international relations have opened avenues for educational exchanges and increased access to global knowledge networks, they have also led to disparities in educational opportunities. Nigeria has faced a significant brain drain, driven by international demand and local challenges, where skilled professionals seek better opportunities abroad. Okebukola (2016) posited that the outflow of educated Nigerians to more developed economies has further deepened the educational divide and negatively impacted local social development.

The global push for market liberalisation has profoundly affected Nigeria’s labour market. While FDI has brought job opportunities, it has also introduced precarious employment conditions. The adoption of

international labour standards and increased competition from global corporations have led to job insecurity, poor wages, and poor working conditions in many sectors (Adewumi, 2001). This trend threatens social stability and impedes efforts to improve living standard.

The interaction between globalisation, international relations and environmental issues presents another snag. Nigeria's drive towards economic development and integration into the global market has come at a significant environmental cost. International demand-driven activities, such as oil exploration have led to environmental degradation, particularly in the Niger Delta region. The resultant ecological damage has not only displaced communities but also fuelled conflicts, disrupting social development initiatives (Onuoha, 2008).

The role of international relations in Nigeria's social development is also reflected in its dependence on foreign aid and loans. While international organisations and donor countries have provided essential resources for social programmes, this dependency has often led to vulnerabilities. Omotola (2010) argued that the conditionalities attached to aid packages undermine Nigeria's policy autonomy and ability to design context-specific social development programmes. This heavy reliance on external aid poses a significant snag in the achievement of sustainable social development.

The significance of this study lies in its examination of the multifaceted effects of globalisation and international relations on social development in Nigeria, highlighting the challenges or "snags" that hinder progress in areas such as economic equity, cultural cohesion, governance, healthcare, education, and environmental sustainability. By providing a comprehensive analysis of these issues, the study offers valuable insights for policymakers, scholars, and stakeholders on the need for context-specific strategies to address the adverse impacts and harness the potential benefits of global integration to achieve more inclusive and sustainable social development.

Statement of the problem

Despite the promises of globalisation and the influence of international relations in fostering development, Nigeria faces persistent social challenges that question the effectiveness of these global processes. Economic liberalisation, promoted by international financial institutions, is expected to spur economic growth and improve social outcomes. However, Nigeria's reality reveals widening income inequality, high levels of poverty, and limited access to basic social services such as health care and education. Globalisation has also brought cultural influences that disrupt traditional values and social cohesion, creating an identity crisis, especially among the youth. Additionally, political pressures and global governance standards have not sufficiently addressed corruption and weak institutions, which continue to undermine the potential for sustainable social development.

Although international relations have facilitated knowledge exchange and foreign investments, they have also led to significant challenges, such as brain drain, environmental degradation, and dependency on foreign aid. The loss of skilled professionals to developed economies, driven by better opportunities abroad, has hampered the growth of critical sectors such as health care and education in Nigeria. Meanwhile, Nigeria's dependence on foreign aid and loans has compromised its policy autonomy, often imposing conditionalities that are ill-suited to local contexts. Environmental issues linked to global demand for oil have resulted in ecological damage, particularly in the Niger Delta, disrupting social development efforts. Hence, this study sets out to ascertain the impact of globalisation and international relations Nigeria's social development and its snags.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study aims to critically examine these problems, exploring how the complex dynamics of globalisation and international relations contribute to the snags in Nigeria's social development. The objectives are to:

1. Examine the impact of globalisation on Nigeria's economic inequality and social cohesion.
2. Assess the influence of international relations on Nigeria's governance and health care systems.
3. Explore the challenges posed by globalisation on education, environmental sustainability and dependency on foreign aid in Nigeria

Globalisation and Economic Inequality in Nigeria

Globalisation, characterised by increased global trade, capital flow and liberal economic policies, has had a significant impact on Nigeria's economic landscape. The implementation of structural adjustment programmes (SAPs) and trade liberalisation policies, driven by global institutions such as the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and World Bank, aimed to integrate Nigeria into the global economy and stimulate growth. However, these economic policies have disproportionately benefited the elite, leading to rising income inequality and social disparity (Adedeji, 2002). Liberalisation often neglects the socioeconomic realities of a country, resulting in the economic marginalisation of the most vulnerable groups (Ake, 2000).

Despite the intention to spur development, globalisation has deepened economic inequalities by prioritising profit maximisation over equitable distribution. For instance, while globalisation has attracted foreign direct investment (FDI) in sectors such as oil and telecommunications, the benefits have remained concentrated in the hands of a few, with limited trickle-down effects to the broader population. According to Ihonvbere (2017), these policies have neglected the informal economy, where most Nigerians find their livelihood, thus widening the gap between the rich and the poor. This skewed development hampers social cohesion and generates socioeconomic tensions within the country.

Furthermore, Nigeria's increased openness to foreign goods and services has adversely affected local industries and small-scale businesses. The influx of cheaper, imported goods has stifled domestic production and led to widespread job losses in sectors that are unable to compete globally. This dynamic has exacerbated poverty and social exclusion coupled with growing income disparities. As Suleiman (2018) observed, Nigeria's unregulated nature of globalisation has led to social instability, thereby undermining sustainable social development.

Cultural Globalisation and Social Development in Nigeria

Cultural globalisation refers to the transmission of ideas, meanings and values across national borders, driven by global media, technology and international exchange. With its diverse ethnic and cultural makeup, Nigeria has experienced significant shifts in cultural practices due to increased exposure to Western ideals and lifestyles. The proliferation of global media platforms and foreign cultural products has led to a gradual erosion of indigenous norms and traditional values, particularly among the youth (Suleiman, 2018). This phenomenon threatens to social cohesion as it disrupts established social structures and weakens the influence of traditional institutions.

The growing influence of Western culture, fashion, and entertainment on Nigerian society is particularly evident in urban areas, where the youth are often more exposed to global media. While this exposure fosters cultural exchange and creativity, it has also led to the adoption of foreign values that clash with traditional norms. According to Falola (2020), this cultural shift has generated an identity crisis, creating generational divides and leading to cultural heritage loss. This dissonance impacts social development efforts by weakening the communal bonds that form the foundation of Nigerian society.

Moreover, cultural globalisation has affected traditional family structures and social norms, altering perceptions of gender roles, family values and community responsibilities. The breakdown of these cultural norms, which have traditionally supported community cohesion, has led to an increase in the number of cases of social deviance, disillusionment, and unrest among young Nigerians. Scholars argue that these cultural changes,

driven by unchecked globalisation, undermine social stability and complicate efforts to promote inclusive social development (Suleiman, 2018).

Globalisation, Health Sector Reforms, and Nigeria's Social Welfare

Globalisation has facilitated the diffusion of medical advancements and international health policies, contributing to Nigeria's health care sector reform. Through international partnerships, Nigeria has gained access to critical medical knowledge, technologies, and donor support to combat HIV/AIDS and malaria. However, the influence of global economic policies has also led to the privatisation of health care services, limiting access to quality care for low-income populations. The neoliberal policies advocated by global institutions have encouraged the commercialisation of healthcare, thereby worsening social inequality (Alubo, 2003).

The commercialisation trend, driven by global economic norms, has led to the growth of private health care facilities catering to the wealthy, while public health care services have suffered from underfunding and neglect. This unequal access to health care services poses significant challenges to social welfare, as most Nigerians rely on public health care facilities. Onuoha (2008) elicits that the shift towards privatisation has placed a financial burden on the poor, making it difficult for them to afford basic medical services and thereby undermining social development efforts.

The impact of globalisation on health care extends to the emigration of skilled health professionals in search of better opportunities abroad, a phenomenon known as brain drain. This migration trend has left public hospitals severely understaffed, leading to inadequate service delivery and poor health outcomes. Okebukola (2016) argues that brain drain, driven by global demand for skilled workers, not only undermines the health care system but also limits the development of Nigeria's human capital, which is crucial for sustainable social development.

Dependency on Foreign Aid and Nigeria's Economic Vulnerability

Through foreign aid and international loans, international relations play a critical role in shaping Nigeria's development agenda. Foreign aid has been vital in supporting Nigeria's social programmes, particularly in health and education. However, the conditionalities attached to aid packages often undermine Nigeria's policy autonomy, resulting in the adoption of externally driven reforms that are not always suited to local realities (Omotola, 2010). This reliance on foreign aid compromises Nigeria's ability to pursue self-sustained social development initiatives and renders it vulnerable to external influences.

The dependency on foreign aid also reflects Nigeria's economic vulnerability despite the face of global market shifts. Nigeria's integration into the global economy has been primarily driven by its oil exports, making it susceptible to fluctuations in global oil prices. Onuoha (2008) stated that this reliance on a single commodity has exposed the country to economic shocks, leading to budget deficits and reduced spending on social services. The resultant economic instability hampers the capacity of the government to invest in long-term social development projects.

Moreover, the influence of international financial institutions in shaping Nigeria's development policies has been a double-edged sword. While loans and aid packages have supported key social programmes, the austerity measures and structural adjustments imposed by these institutions have often led to reduced funding for education, healthcare, and social welfare. Ihonvbere (2017) noted that these external influences restrict Nigeria's policy space and prioritise short-term economic gains over comprehensive social development. This dynamic underscores the importance of reducing aid dependency and building internal resilience to achieve sustainable social progress.

Dependency Theory

This theory was popularised by Latin American scholars such as Raúl Prebisch in the late 1950s and 1960s. Other key contributors include Andre Gunder Frank, Fernando Henrique Cardoso, and Samir Amin. This theory posits that developing countries (referred to as the "periphery") are dependent on developed countries (the "core") due to unequal economic and political relations established through historical colonisation, trade, and global capitalism. According to this theory, developed nations exploit developing countries by controlling trade terms, capital flow, and technology transfer, thereby perpetuating a cycle of underdevelopment. Dependency theorists argue that the global capitalist system benefits the core at the expense of the periphery, leading to a situation in which developing nations remain economically dependent and underdeveloped (Frank, 1966).

This theory assumes that the global economic structure is inherently unequal and favours developed countries. It also assumes that external factors, such as trade policies, foreign investments, and aid conditionalities reinforce and perpetuate the dependency of developing countries on the developed world. The theory posits that developing nations like Nigeria cannot achieve genuine social and economic development without a restructuring of the global economic system (Amin, 1976). Critics of this theory argue that it offers a deterministic and overly simplistic explanation of underdevelopment. It has been critiqued for downplaying internal factors such as governance, corruption, and domestic policies, which also contribute to nation's underdevelopment. Additionally, critics contend that the theory does not account for cases where developing nations, such as the East Asian Tigers have successfully integrated into the global economy and achieved growth (Evans, 1979). Modern scholars also criticise the theory for being overly pessimistic about the prospects for development within the global capitalist framework's prospects for development.

This theory is highly relevant to this study as it offers a theoretical lens to understand Nigeria's social and economic challenges in the context of globalisation and international relations. The theory highlights how Nigeria's dependence on foreign aid, unequal trade terms, and global financial institutions perpetuates economic inequality, environmental degradation, and social instability. This study can explore how global policies and economic liberalisation contribute to the widening income gap, cultural erosion, and weakened social services in Nigeria by employing. This theory. Furthermore, it provides insight into the external constraints on Nigeria's social development efforts and the need for policies that promote self-reliance and sustainable development.

Empirical Review

Adedeji (2002) conducted a study on "Trade Liberalisation and Inequality in Africa: A Case Study of Nigeria." This study examined the impact of trade liberalisation policies on income distribution and social inequality in Nigeria. This study employed a quantitative approach using secondary data on income distribution, poverty rates, and economic growth from national statistical agencies and the World Bank. The effects of trade policies through regression models to determine their relationship with inequality levels. The study found that trade liberalisation increased income inequality in Nigeria due to the uneven distribution of economic benefits, primarily favouring the elite and foreign investors. It revealed that liberalisation led to the neglect of small-scale industries and intensified social disparities.

Both the reviewed and current studies focus on the economic impact of globalisation on inequality and its consequences for Nigeria's social development. While the reviewed study focused specifically on trade liberalisation policies, the current study examines a broader scope of globalisation influences, including cultural impacts and health care reforms.

Suleiman (2018) conducted a study on “The Impact of Globalisation on Nigerian Cultural Values: A Sociological Perspective.” This study explored the influence of globalisation on Nigerian society’ cultural values and social norms, particularly among youths. The study used a qualitative research approach, conducting semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions with youths, traditional leaders, and cultural scholars in selected urban areas of Nigeria. It analysed the data using thematic content analysis. The study revealed that globalisation led to the erosion of traditional values and increased adoption of Western cultural practices, resulting in identity crises and weakened social cohesion. The findings indicated that the cultural shift was more prominent among urban youth who were more exposed to global media.

The reviewed study and the pioneer study are related because both studies focus on the cultural impact of globalisation and its effects on social cohesion and development in Nigeria. The area of difference is that the reviewed study solely focused on cultural globalisation, whereas the current study incorporates other dimensions such as economic and health care influences on social development.

Okebukola (2016) conducted on “The Brain Drain Phenomenon in Africa: Implications for Higher Education and Development.” This study assessed the effects of brain drain on Nigeria’s the higher education sector and social development. The study utilised a mixed-method approach, combining university administrators and lecturers’ surveys with secondary data on migration trends and educational statistics. Descriptive statistics and qualitative analysis were used to interpret the findings. The study found that brain drain has led to a shortage of skilled professionals in Nigeria’s education and health care sectors, hampering the quality of service delivery and human capital development. The findings highlighted the push factors, including poor working conditions and low remuneration, as key drivers of skilled worker migration. Both studies address the issue of brain drain and its negative implications for Nigeria’s social development, focusing on how the loss of skilled professionals affects key sectors. The reviewed study specifically examined brain drain in the context of higher education, whereas the current study extends the analysis to broader globalisation factors affecting multiple social development areas, including economic policies and environmental issues.

The literature review highlights the complex and multifaceted impact of globalisation and international relations on social development in Nigeria. It reveals how economic liberalisation has exacerbated income inequality, cultural globalisation has eroded traditional values and how international relations have influenced sectors such as health care and education through policies and aid dependencies. However, while existing studies provide valuable insights into the individual effects of these global forces, a significant gap exists in the integrated analysis of Nigeria’s overall social development in terms of economic, cultural, and policy dimensions. This study addresses this gap by offering a comprehensive exploration of the combined influence of globalisation and international relations on Nigeria’s social development, focusing on the “snags” or challenges that hinder sustainable progress.

Methodology

This study employed a qualitative research methodology to explore the impact of globalisation and international relations on Nigeria’s social development, specifically focusing on the perspectives of scholars in the fields of mass communication and international relations. The target population consisted of Nigerian academic scholars, researchers, and practitioners with backgrounds in mass communication and international relations. A purposive sampling technique was used to select participants with relevant expertise and experience in these domains, ensuring that the insights gathered reflected several perspectives on the issues being examined. The sample size was determined to be 10 participants, which is deemed adequate for achieving qualitative data saturation while allowing for diverse viewpoints.

Semi-structured interviews were used to collect data, allowing for in-depth discussions and flexibility in exploring participants' views on the interplay between globalisation, international relations and social development. Each interview lasted approximately 45-60 minutes and was conducted either in person or via video conferencing platforms to accommodate the availability of the participants. Audio recordings of the interviews were transcribed for analysis. The data analysis method employed thematic analysis, enabling the identification of common themes, patterns, and insights across the responses. This approach facilitated a comprehensive understanding of how globalisation and international relations affect social development in Nigeria, highlighting the challenges and opportunities identified by the interviewed scholars. By synthesising these perspectives, this study contributes to the broader discourse on the implications of global dynamics for social progress in developing countries.

Data Presentation and Analysis

The researchers adopted thematic method of data analysis to analyse the data gathered from the in-depth interviews. Themes were deduced deductively following the research objectives. The following themes were deduced: how globalisation contributes to economic inequality and affects social cohesion in Nigeria; ways international relations impact governance and health care development in Nigeria and challenges that globalisation poses to education, environmental sustainability and foreign aid dependency in Nigeria. These are presented and discussed as follows:

How Globalisation contributes to Inequality and affects Social Cohesion in Nigeria; The interview report has shown that globalisation has significantly impacted the economic landscape of Nigeria, often worsening existing inequalities. While it has led to an influx of foreign investment and access to global markets, the benefits of such economic activities have not been equitably distributed. The liberalisation of trade policies favoured large corporations and wealthy individuals, leaving marginalised communities without the means to effectively compete in the global market. This unequal distribution of wealth has resulted in a widening income gap, as those who are already economically advantaged can leverage globalisation to further their wealth, while the poor continue to struggle for basic necessities.

Moreover, the interviewees stated that globalisation has contributed to the erosion of local industries due to the influx of cheaper imported goods. Many local businesses, unable to compete with foreign products, have been closed, leading to job losses and increased unemployment. This decline in local economic activity affects not only individual livelihoods but also has broader implications for social cohesion. Social ties can weaken as communities face economic hardships, leading to increased tensions and divisions within society. The inability of local businesses to thrive under the pressures of globalisation has contributed to a sense of disenfranchisement among the populace, further straining social relations.

The interviewees agreed that cultural globalisation compounds the issue of economic inequality by promoting values and lifestyles that may conflict with traditional norms. The rapid adoption of foreign cultural practices, particularly among the youth, has led to cultural dissonance that can undermine social cohesion. The interviewees illustrated that this cultural shift creates generational divides, as older generations may resist changes perceived as threatening to their values, while younger individuals embrace global influences. This dynamic can foster a sense of alienation and conflict within communities, further worsening social tensions already heightened by economic inequality.

The interviewees argued that the effects of globalisation on economic inequality and social cohesion in Nigeria highlight the need for policies that promote equitable growth and social inclusion. Addressing these disparities requires a multifaceted approach that considers globalisation' economic, cultural, and social dimensions. Such

strategies could include supporting local industries, promoting fair trade practices, and fostering cultural preservation initiatives to strengthen community ties and enhance social resilience.

Ways International Relations impact Governance and Healthcare Development in Nigeria; Most of the interviewees believed that international relations significantly shape governance structures and healthcare development in Nigeria, particularly through the influence of global institutions and foreign aid. The partnerships established with international organisations, such as the World Bank and International Monetary Fund, often come with stipulations that require the Nigerian government to implement specific reforms in governance and health care. These conditionalities, while intended to improve transparency and accountability, can sometimes undermine local governance by imposing foreign frameworks that may not align with Nigeria's sociopolitical context. Consequently, the effectiveness of governance can be compromised, leading to a disconnection between government policies and the needs of the population.

The interviewees stated that international relations facilitate knowledge exchange and collaboration in health care development, but they can also perpetuate inequalities within the sector. The influx of foreign aid and international support has been crucial in addressing public health challenges, such as the HIV/AIDS epidemic and maternal health issues. However, reliance on external funding can create vulnerabilities in the healthcare system, as seen during periods of reduced international support or changing global priorities. This dependence can hinder the government's ability to develop sustainable health care policies that adequately address population's unique health needs.

The interviewees posited that the political dynamics of international relations can influence Nigeria's healthcare policies, as foreign nations may prioritise certain health issues based on their geopolitical interests rather than the Nigerian populace's pressing needs. This can lead to misalignment in health care priorities, where resources are allocated to initiatives favoured by foreign donors rather than those that would be most beneficial to local communities. As a result, a disparity often exists between the health outcomes experienced by different segments of the population, particularly in marginalised areas.

Additionally, the interviewees acknowledged that it is essential to critically evaluate the role of international relations in shaping domestic policies to improve governance and healthcare development in Nigeria. By fostering partnerships that respect local contexts and prioritise the needs of the population, Nigeria can work towards achieving a more equitable and effective governance structure and health care system. Strengthening domestic capacity and reducing dependency on foreign aid through sustainable development practices will enhance the governance and healthcare framework resilience in Nigeria.

Challenges Globalisation poses to Education, Environmental Sustainability and Dependence on Foreign Aid in Nigeria.

All the interviewees agreed that Globalisation presents several challenges for Nigeria, particularly in the realms of education, environmental sustainability, and dependency on foreign aid. In the education sector, the influence of globalisation often manifests itself in the promotion of Western educational standards and practices, which may not align with the local context. Exposure to global educational resources can enhance learning opportunities, but it can also lead to the neglect of indigenous knowledge systems and local curricula that are vital for community development. This misalignment can create a workforce that is skilled in globalised competencies but lacks the contextual understanding necessary to address local challenges.

Other interviewees also acknowledged that environmental sustainability is another area where globalisation poses significant challenges for Nigeria. The country's dependence on oil exports, driven by global demand, has led to environmental degradation, particularly in the Niger Delta region. The pursuit of profit in the extractive

industries often results in the neglect of environmental regulations and community rights. This dynamic intensifies social inequalities, as marginalised communities suffer the consequences of pollution and habitat destruction, further entrenching poverty and social instability. The lack of effective environmental governance, compounded by globalisation's pressures, makes it difficult for Nigeria to achieve its sustainable development goals.

Additionally, the interviewees argued that Nigeria's dependency on foreign aid has intensified in the context of globalisation. While foreign aid is often essential for funding social programmes and development initiatives, it can create a cycle of dependency cycle that undermines local capacity building and self-reliance. The conditionalities attached to aid often prioritise the interests of donor countries over the needs of the Nigerian populace, leading to policies that may not be conducive to long-term development. This dependency limits Nigeria's policy autonomy and inhibits the government's ability to develop home-grown solutions that address its unique socioeconomic challenges.

The interviewees believed that addressing the challenges posed by globalisation requires a strategic approach that emphasises the importance of local contexts and sustainable practices. Nigeria must focus on strengthening its education system by integrating indigenous knowledge, promoting environmental stewardship, and reducing dependency on foreign aid. Nigeria can navigate the complexities of globalisation while striving for a more equitable and sustainable future by fostering a sense of ownership and responsibility among citizens and policymakers.

Discussion of the Findings

The findings indicated that globalisation significantly contributes to economic inequality and challenges social cohesion in Nigeria, as trade policy liberalisation tends to favour wealthy individuals and foreign corporations, thereby widening the income gap and fostering cultural dissonance among communities, particularly between the younger and older generations. The findings of the study also align with that of Adedeji (2002) who stated that trade liberalisation increased income inequality in Nigeria due to the uneven distribution of economic benefits, primarily favouring the elite and foreign investors. It also revealed that liberalisation led to the neglect of small-scale industries and intensified social disparities. The findings related to contribution of globalisation to the challenges of economic inequality and social cohesion in Nigeria are relevant to dependency theory, which posits that the global economic system benefits wealthy nations and elite individuals within developing countries, thereby perpetuating a cycle of dependence and underdevelopment that exacerbates social disparities and cultural tensions. The findings related to contribution of globalisation to the challenges of economic inequality and social cohesion in Nigeria suggest that if current trends continue, the widening income gap may lead to increased social unrest and instability, making it imperative for policymakers to design inclusive economic strategies that promote equitable wealth distribution and cultural understanding to foster social harmony.

Furthermore, the study revealed that international relations critically impact governance and health care development in Nigeria by imposing external frameworks that often do not align with local needs, thereby undermining the effectiveness of governance and creating dependencies on foreign aid that can compromise the sustainability of health care policies. This finding is consistent with that of Suleiman (2018) who demonstrated that globalisation led to the erosion of traditional values and increased adoption of Western cultural practices, resulting in identity crises and weakened social cohesion. The findings indicated that the cultural shift was more prominent among urban youth who were most exposed to global media. In the context of international relations and their impact on governance and healthcare development in Nigeria, dependency theory is particularly

relevant because it highlights how the imposition of external frameworks and conditionalities from foreign aid and international organisations can undermine local governance and hinder the development of self-reliant health care policies, ultimately reinforcing Nigeria's dependency on external actors for its governance and social service needs. The findings concerning the impact international relations on governance and health care development indicate that Nigeria's reliance on external frameworks and foreign aid can undermine the effectiveness of domestic policies, highlighting the urgent need for a shift towards self-reliance and local governance that prioritises community needs to improve public health outcomes and overall governance effectiveness.

Finally, the findings illustrated that globalisation presents substantial challenges to education, environmental sustainability and foreign aid dependency in Nigeria, as the promotion of Western educational standards can neglect indigenous knowledge, the exploitation of natural resources for global markets leads to environmental degradation and the reliance on foreign aid can inhibit local capacity building and long-term development solutions. This confirms Okebukola (2016) findings that brain drain has led to a shortage of skilled professionals in Nigeria's education and healthcare sectors, thereby hampering the quality of service delivery and human capital development. The findings also highlighted the push factors, including poor working conditions and low remuneration, as key drivers of skilled workers migration. The findings concerning the challenges globalisation poses to education, environmental sustainability, and foreign aid dependency in Nigeria resonate with dependency theory, which asserts that the dominance of global forces and Western standards can lead to the marginalisation of local knowledge and practices, while the exploitation of natural resources for global profit perpetuates environmental degradation and deepens the cycle of dependency on foreign aid, thereby limiting Nigeria's capacity for sustainable development and self-determination. The findings on the challenges globalisation poses to education, environmental sustainability and foreign aid dependency suggest that Nigeria risks perpetuating a cycle of dependency and underdevelopment that compromises its future growth and environmental health without a concerted effort to integrate indigenous knowledge into educational frameworks, promote sustainable practices, and reduce reliance on external funding.

Conclusion

The study concluded that while offering economic opportunities, globalisation has primarily deepened existing economic inequalities and strained social cohesion in Nigeria. The disproportionate benefits of globalisation favour the small elite, leaving much of the population behind and worsening cultural dissonance, which poses a risk to long-term social stability. The study established that Nigeria's governance and health care development have been significantly shaped by international relations, often through external frameworks and foreign aid that do not fully align with local needs. This reliance on international actors has highlighted the need for Nigeria to strengthen its governance structures and build a more self-sufficient health care system to ensure sustainability and effectiveness. Finally, the study justified that globalisation presents notable challenges to Nigeria's education sector, environmental sustainability and foreign aid dependency. The findings show that without strategic efforts to incorporate local knowledge, enforce environmental protection, and foster financial independence, the adverse impacts of globalisation could hinder Nigeria's overall development and self-reliance in the long term.

This study contributes to the body of knowledge by providing a nuanced understanding of the impact of globalisation and international relations on Nigeria's social development, particularly in the context of economic inequality, governance, health care, education and environmental sustainability. By employing dependency theory as a theoretical framework, this study elucidates how global forces perpetuate dependence

and intensify social disparities within Nigeria. The findings highlighted that globalisation, while offering opportunities for economic engagement, often reinforces existing inequalities and cultural tensions, emphasising the need for a critical examination of the mechanisms through which these global influences operate. This study fills a crucial gap in the literature by integrating various dimensions of globalisation and international relations, rather than isolating them, to offer a comprehensive view of their collective effects on Nigerian society.

Furthermore, the research underscores the importance of local context in developing effective responses to the challenges posed by globalisation. By identifying the limitations of foreign aid and external governance frameworks, this study advocates for policies that prioritise local capacity building and sustainable development initiatives. The insights garnered from scholars in mass communication and international relations provide valuable perspectives that can inform policymakers, educators, and development practitioners seeking to navigate the complexities of globalisation in a manner that promotes equitable growth and social resilience. Ultimately, this research enhances the discourse on globalisation and social development, contributing to a deeper understanding of how developing countries such as Nigeria can leverage global dynamics while fostering sustainable progress.

Recommendations

In view of the findings for this study, the following recommendations have been made.

- 1) The Nigerian government should implement inclusive economic policies that prioritise the development of local industries and equitable wealth distribution to mitigate the adverse effects of globalisation on economic inequality and social cohesion.
- 2) Nigeria should foster stronger local governance frameworks and enhance the sustainability of health care policies by reducing reliance on foreign aid, allowing for greater alignment with the population unique needs.
- 3) Nigeria should integrate indigenous knowledge into the educational curriculum, promote environmentally sustainable practices, and develop innovative financing mechanisms to reduce dependence on foreign aid, thereby empowering local communities to achieve self-reliance and sustainable development.

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